

" TOSHMASJID " COMPLEX

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Kiziltepa district Citizens of Toshmasjid neighborhood in the gathering located in the " Toshmasjid " complex of Uzbekistan Navoi province Kiziltepa district Wangozi in the town monument (XVI century) Many columnar big from the room a single jome consisting of is a mosque . 2 large ones and 16 ones kind of small domes with closed . Various in size from the domes organize found column-domed constructions to himself special _ Head style to the east in front of the facing mosque height raised tower (height 24 meters) Medium in Asia preserved the rest of the 16th century about that's it kind of of structures the most tall and elegance is counted . Some researchers Stone mosque in the 16th century by Abdullah Khan II built if it is said , others The tower in the complex dates back to the 18th century about said thought means _ Building (24x40 meters) south and western in the form of G from the side built series from buildings consists of West in the part Stone mosque , madrasa, ablution hall and bathroom located _ Stone mosque complex high (about 70 centimeters) platform on top of it built and the front stretched out gone majestic is a building . Central in the part tall decorative roof and big blue the dome separate stands _

Stone mosque complex in the 16th century set up done _ Around 1580s Khojayi Kalonkhoja the mosque again to build decree gave _ This construction six year continue reached and completed in 1585-1586 . Building in construction complete ripe from brick used . Old meticulous buildings broke instead of _ new columnar hall built _ Complex to build for a flat place is selected , of the object eastern by ditch flowing past , northern on the side road available , of the complex southern in the part cemetery located _ This is it complex plan in 1949 an architect A. Balayev calculations based on built _ In 1935 in the complex internal without a yard , two destroyed the multi-story madrasa thrown _ Balayev own in the design broke indicating the location of the sent madrasa past _ The size of the mosque is 24x40 m common 2 large in the building and 16 ones kind of small domes with closed there is also a room [2]. The building is 29x29x5

cm size rectangle in the form set up done _

The floors are made of bricks laid down . Stone mosque in the complex to a height of 24 m There is a minaret . Bottom in the part foundation diameter 3.8m, base of stone typed . State in 1982 protected. " Moscow" collective farm and Kiziltepa district leaders , Culture of the Uzbek SSR works Ministry command with with Stone mosque complex partially repaired . In the complex museum organize done _ People in 2002 deputies Navoi region Council out of line except in the session President Islam Karimov Stone mosque about thought after stating , the region governor B. Roziyev to the command according to repair works started _ Reconstruction works for five months reached _

Stone mosque complex next to height was 24 m Wangozi tower located _ This tower was built during rule Shaibani Abdullah Khan II

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